

Migratory Crossroads: predicting the dynamics of a great vertical migration in a changing habitat

1. Excellence

Vertical migration of zooplankton signifies the greatest synchronized animal movement of our planet¹. In the northern Norwegian coast and adjacent oceanic areas of Norwegian and Barents Seas (study area: Fig. 1), a tiny herbivorous copepod named *Calanus finmarchicus* (Fig. 1) performs two different vertical migrations. These include daily vertical movements of tens-to-hundreds of meters (diel vertical migration, DVM) and seasonal movements of hundreds-to-thousands of meters (seasonal vertical migration, SVM) in response to corresponding variations of irradiance (visible light), temperature, food availability and visual predation risk². DVM & SVM play a paramount ecological and economic role in the study area because: (i) vertical behaviour, abundance and phenology of many commercially harvested fish species are linked to these migrations^{3,4} and (ii) vertical migrations significantly contribute to the export of atmospheric CO₂ into the ocean's deep interior^{5,6} – a key process in the buffering of global climate change (biological carbon pump)⁷. Nonetheless, anthropogenic climate change has accelerated beyond natural buffers and much of the routine environmental variability of the study area is shifting at unprecedented rates, where *C. finmarchicus* will encounter warmer seawater temperatures, increased feeding opportunities, altered underwater light regimes and higher visual predation risk towards the end of this century⁸⁻¹⁰. Unfortunately, we have poor understanding of how vertical migrations would respond to these environmental shifts – especially when environmental variables exert cumulative impacts on zooplankton behaviour and life-histories. If climate-change-related environmental shifts drive substantial changes in *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations, their ecological and economic benefits could arrive at crucial crossroads. The proposed project, 'Migratory Crossroads' thus aims to investigate how *C. finmarchicus* DVM & SVM would respond to environmental shifts expected in a highly productive and sensitive marine habitat.

1.1 State of the art, knowledge needs and project objectives

DVM of *C. finmarchicus* is an irradiance-driven behaviour with a night-time feeding ascent to food-rich surface waters and a daytime descent to deeper darker waters to take refuge from visually orientating planktivorous fish (visual predators)¹¹ (Fig. 2). DVM is prominent during the productive season (spring-summer) when diel irradiance variations are most notable¹². Although higher food concentrations and temperatures should generally promote DVM^{13,14}, *C. finmarchicus* DVMs in the study area remain weak during much of the productive season, when they aggregate densely closer to the sea surface^{15,16}. Despite the mechanism underlying this non-migratory behaviour being unknown, high-risk near-surface aggregations are likely enabled by lower visual predation risks typically encountered at higher latitudes^{17,18}. Irrespective of DVM, the growth, development and reproduction of *C. finmarchicus* predominantly occur during the productive season, which lasts for ca. 6–8 months in the study area¹⁹, during which they may produce 2–3 generations²⁰. However, as reduction of food supply constrains the growth and development of later generations of *C. finmarchicus*, their advanced developmental stages synthesize high-energy lipid compounds that can act as an energy reserve. When food supply fades towards the unproductive season (autumn-winter), they descend to greater depths (> 1000 m in the Norwegian Sea²¹) with the stored lipids and enter a state of hibernation, termed diapause^{22,23}. Towards the onset of the next productive season, diapause terminates, and post-diapause stages gradually ascend to the upper pelagial, moult into adults and reproduce – thus completing their SVM²⁴ (Fig. 2). While food availability is the main driver of SVM, temperature and visual predation risk can significantly modulate its periodicity (timing) and amplitude (depth). For example, when the predation risk imposed by Norwegian spring-spawning herring increases, SVM of *C. finmarchicus* in the Norwegian Sea occurs earlier in the year and extend to greater depths where predators may not routinely enter^{4,25}. Further, as the metabolic rate (= the energy reserve depletion rate) is temperature-dependent²⁶, diapause duration and the timing of seasonal ascent are determined by the ambient temperature at diapause habitats. Consequently, *C. finmarchicus* tends to diapause at colder parts of the water column²⁷.

Although we have a reasonable understanding of how irradiance, temperature, food availability and visual predation risk individually influence the vertical migrations of *C. finmarchicus*, their cumulative impacts are not known. For example, in a hypothetical habitat where irradiance, temperature, food concentration and visual predation risk increase concurrently, based on the current understanding, one could predict that DVM will

Fig. 1 The study area (left) together with *C. finmarchicus* (CF) – a key food source for Barents Sea capelin, Norwegian spring-spawning herring and northeast-Arctic cod, saithe & haddock. All species are commercially harvested. Dashed arrows: predate on *C. finmarchicus* at their early developmental stages. Figure not to scale.

Fig. 2 Duality of *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations. While DVM (A) is largely restricted to the productive season, SVM (B) and diapause of older developmental stages occur as food supply is cut-off during the unproductive season. Figure not to scale.

and positive food-effect does not necessarily balance out the negative temperature-effect in a warmer, food-rich environment³³. Further, *C. finmarchicus* body size evolves under size-dependent visual predation risk, which may increase or decrease depending on the size-selectivity of the planktivore³⁴. The body size significantly influences the periodicity and amplitude of DVM^{35,36} & SVM³⁷⁻³⁹ mainly through: (i) allometric relationships (where, larger individuals tend to migrate frequently and deeper compared to smaller ones) and (ii) generation time implication (where smaller individuals produce additional generations before seasonal descent to diapause). Therefore, a proper characterization of body size-environment interactions is needed to predict vertical migration-environment interactions.

In our study area (Fig. 1), models predict elevated heat flux from the atmosphere to the ocean⁴⁰ and a trend of persistent above-average North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), which increases the inflow of warmer Atlantic Water^{41,42}. This will result in a 1–3 °C temperature increase in the upper-pelagial where the northern stretches of the study area will be free of sea ice⁹, which will collectively increase the pelagic primary production⁴³. Further, deeper waters of the Norwegian Sea have been warming at a rate of *ca.* 0.01 °C yr⁻¹, which could lead to a temperature rise of 0.5–0.7 °C by the end of this century^{8,44}. While the loss of sea ice will allow a better subsurface light penetration and thus enhance the efficiency of visual predation⁴⁵, planktivorous fish, such as Atlantic mackerel will frequently migrate north-eastwards along the Norwegian coast in search of better feeding opportunities⁴⁶. Warmer waters are expected to increase the abundance of northeast Arctic cod and Norwegian spring-spawning herring (which predate on *C. finmarchicus* at least at some point of their life cycle: Fig. 1) in both coastal and oceanic regions^{47,48}. If these predictions hold, *C. finmarchicus* in the study area should encounter significant increase of growth potential & mortality risk and sub-optimal (warmer) diapause conditions during the next 50–70 years.

Although vertical behavioural responses of *C. finmarchicus* against these future environmental shifts are unknown, two generic scenarios can be hypothesized. First, in a modulation scenario, modest shifts of bottom-up and top-down selection pressures may be counteracted by modulations (plasticity) of *C. finmarchicus* vertical behaviour^{14,34}. This may lead to general intensification of DVM & SVM, which can in turn enhance the vertical carbon export to the deeper ocean⁴⁹. Second, in a crossroad scenario where size-dependent visual predation risk can increase significantly beyond behavioural tolerance^{14,34}, (as visual predators target larger and conspicuous prey) the body size of *C. finmarchicus* would decrease and DVM & SVM intensities may also diminish, thus leading to reduced vertical carbon export to the deeper ocean⁵⁰. Since the cumulative impact of expected environmental shifts on *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations have not been assessed before, we do not know which of these scenarios or any other unprecedented scenario (e.g., reverse vertical migrations⁵¹, schooling¹⁷) is more likely.

intensify and SVM will tend to occur earlier in the year and extend to greater depths. However, two interactive forcings makes it difficult to generate straightforward predictions. First, it is the DVM-SVM interaction, where periodicity and amplitude changes in one migration tends to drive corresponding changes in the other. Here, more intense DVM leads to delayed growth & development and slower reserve accumulation rates²⁸. This in turn delays the timing of SVM (seasonal descent) because it takes more time to develop to an advanced developmental stage with

sufficient energy reserves to last the diapause^{13,29}. Second, there is the selection pressure interaction, where co-varying environmental variables impose contrasting selection pressures on *C. finmarchicus* – i.e., food availability and temperature (collectively, the growth potential) in the bottom-up and mortality risk imposed by visual predators in the top-down³⁰. Irradiance, on the other hand, influences both in the bottom-up and top-down as it enhances the growth potential (by driving pelagic primary production) as well as the detection efficiency of visually orientating planktivores. Interconnecting these contrasting selection pressures is a master life-history trait, body size³¹. *C. finmarchicus* body size increases with food concentration but decreases with temperature (*cf.* the temperature-size rule³²),

Therefore, the overarching objective of Migratory Crossroads is to develop a comprehensive understanding of the vertical migratory responses of *C. finmarchicus* to the cumulative impacts of climate-change-related irradiance, temperature, food availability and visual predation risk environmental shifts expected in the future.

To achieve the overarching objective, we focus on a hybrid mechanistic-empirical approach, where: (i) a mechanistic model running at high spatial, temporal and biological resolution will be used to simulate the behavioural (DVM & SVM) & life-history (body size) patterns of *C. finmarchicus* and their ecological consequences under present and future environmental conditions, and (ii) the predictive potential of the model will be improved by validating it with empirical data of comparable resolution. The spatial coverage of Migratory Crossroads extends in three-dimensions (3D) across the study area covering its entire depth range (Fig. 1) and the temporal coverage extends from present-day towards the end of this century. The overarching objective is split into four specific objectives (SOs) as:

SO1: Developing a high-resolution mechanistic simulation model that allows an unconstrained representation of *C. finmarchicus* diel and seasonal vertical migrations.

SO2: Improving predictive potential of the above mechanistic model using empirical data with comparable spatial, temporal and biological resolution.

SO3: Using the improved model to predict future diel & seasonal vertical migrations and the resultant ecological consequences of *C. finmarchicus* under the cumulative impact of irradiance, temperature, food and predation environmental shifts expected in the study area.

SO4: Ensuring that the data, models and methods of WPs 1–3 are properly managed and openly available, and project findings are effectively communicated to target audiences.

1.2 Research questions and hypotheses, theoretical approach and methodology

We designed four integrated work packages (WPs) to address each of these SOs. While WPs 1, 2 and 3 orient on specific research questions (RQs) and scientific hypothesis testing (H), WP4 oversees data management and communications of the project.

WP1: An unconstrained mechanistic simulation model for *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations

Members: Bandara (lead, APN), Pompeii (MIT), Bedington (APN), Wallhead (NIVA), Varpe (mentor, NINA)

RQ1: Can a model with an unconstrained behavioural (DVM & SVM) and life history (body size) representation produce reasonable simulations of present-day *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations in the study area?

H1: An unconstrained mechanistic simulation model for *C. finmarchicus* along with input variables; irradiance, temperature, food availability and visual predation risk can produce, as per the current literature, a general representation of present-day DVM (**H1.1**), SVM (**H1.2**) and vertical carbon export (**H1.3**) of the study area.

Approach: As long timeseries capturing both diel & seasonal vertical migrations of *C. finmarchicus* are rare, the best solution for investigating climate-change-driven dynamics of these migrations is through mechanistic simulation models. Such models operating across the vertical dimension (unidimensional, 1D) can produce data with high spatial (*ca.* 1 m), temporal (*ca.* 1 h) and biological (individual-level) resolution. To study spatio-temporal patterns of emergent behaviour, 1D models can be advected across time and geographic space when they are coupled to 3D ocean circulation models. To date, multiple mechanistic simulation models have been used to study the impacts of the expected 21st century environmental shifts on the abundance⁵², geographic redistribution⁵³ and growth & development patterns⁵⁴ and diapause strategies⁵⁵ of *C. finmarchicus* in the north Atlantic. However, in these models, DVM & SVM of *C. finmarchicus* are either entirely disregarded due to simplicity of the model or because the model is based on sea-surface environmental predictions, or overly simplified by imposing hard constraints on migratory timing and amplitude. Therefore, previous modelling attempts do not shed light on: (i) potential changes of DVM & SVM dynamics of *C. finmarchicus* and (ii) the ensued vertical carbon export to deeper ocean in response to climate-change-related environmental shifts expected in future high-latitude oceans and seas. In WP1, we address this key limitation by developing a 1D mechanistic simulation model that allows an unconstrained representation of DVM & SVM of *C. finmarchicus* and advecting it across the study area using outputs of a 3D ocean circulation model to study the present-day spatio-temporal dynamics of emergent behaviours and vertical carbon export. This modelling system will be our baseline for generating future predictions in subsequent WPs.

Methodology: The framework of our 1D biological model will be adopted from an existing individual-based model (IBM) for *C. finmarchicus*, which was designed mainly by Bandara (lead WP1) in 2018¹³ and rigorously tested for environmental sensitivity and robustness through two subsequent upgrades^{34,56}. It simulates the entire life cycle of *C. finmarchicus* with an adjustable vertical spatial and temporal resolution (minimum = 1 m & 1 h). The IBM allows individuals to freely adjust the periodicity and amplitude of their DVM & SVM, where bottom-

up and top-down selection pressures determine the optimal vertical migrations for a given environment. This unconstrained behavioural representation has been made possible by the unconstrained plasticity and simulated evolution of body size allowed in the model, which is linked to behaviour through allometric relationships (DVM & SVM) and generation time implications (SVM). In **WP1**, we will replace the individual-based construct of the IBM with a super-individual-based (SIBM) construct⁵⁷. Super-individuals represent cohorts of individuals with similar behavioural and life history patterns. Based on our experience, nesting of *ca.* 10^5 individuals in a super-individual will allow us to simulate near-realistic population sizes of *C. finmarchicus* in the study area, capped only by resource limitation and mortality. Irradiance, temperature, phytoplankton concentration (in volumetric carbon units) and visual predation risk are the key forcings in the SIBM that drive the behavioural and life-history patterns of super-individuals. We will rigorously test the SIBM in a simplified 1D model environment by tuning and switching-off environmental variables to test how DVM & SVM strategies emerge under different selection pressures. Since biomass of the biological model is expressed in carbon units, we will estimate the carbon exported below the photic zone by vertically migrating *C. finmarchicus* under different environmental selection pressures.

To advect the 1D SIBM across the study area, we will adopt forcings (see below) from a 3D ocean circulation model (Regional Ocean Modelling Systems, ROMS⁵⁸) coupled to a biogeochemical model (European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model, ERSEM⁵⁹), which runs on a 20-km grid (A20: Norwegian Meteorological Institute). This ROMS-ERSEM (A20) configuration has already been run for present-day scenario (2015-2024) as a part of the EU-funded project TAPAS⁶⁰ (Tools for Assessment and Planning of Aquaculture Sustainability). In **WP1**, we will reuse TAPAS model runs and extract time- and space-specific seawater velocity components, irradiance, temperature and phytoplankton concentrations over the annual cycle for the study area. From these runs, we shall use the OpenDrift Lagrangian particle tracking model⁶¹ to extract time- and space-specific seawater velocity components, irradiance, temperature and phytoplankton concentrations along particle tracks over the annual cycle for our study area (offline coupling). These environmental variables will act as forcings for the 1D SIBM. The selection of representative tracks in the 3D model will be informed by calculation of the Lagrangian Coherent Structures (LCS) from a large ensemble of particles from which a subset will be chosen to force the 1D SIBM.

To achieve **SO1**, a representation of visual predation dynamics of the study area is needed alongside the environmental variables described above. However, since there are no empirical estimates of visual predation risk that align with the spatio-temporal coverage and resolution prescribed by our model, multiple instances of the model (simulation experiments) will be run for the different forcings resembling various visual predation risk intensities and configurations (spatio-temporal dynamics). In the 1D SIBM, visual predation intensity is controlled by a tuneable attribute ranging from 0–1 (which translates to survival probabilities of individuals)⁵⁶. We shall vary this attribute in time and space based on observed present-day spatio-temporal patterns of the dominant visual predators of *C. finmarchicus* (Fig. 1) from literature⁶² and from acoustic and fish trawl survey data from ICES database⁶³. These simulation experiments will allow us to test how varying levels of predation risk may interact with prescribed levels of irradiance, temperature, and food availability in driving different DVM & SVM behaviours and life-history patterns of *C. finmarchicus* in the study area. Further, we will estimate the total annual particulate organic carbon exported below the photic zone by vertically migrating *C. finmarchicus* throughout the study area in each of these simulation experiments. To test **H1**, we will compare the emergent periodicity & amplitude of DVM (**H1.1**), SVM (**H1.2**) and the ensued vertical carbon export (**H1.3**) with published literature to check if they are in reasonable agreement with corresponding natural variability.

Deliverables: 1D SIBM for *C. finmarchicus* (**D1.1**), Modelled present-day environmental dynamics of the study area (**D1.2**), Lagrangian model-coupling framework (**D1.3**), Coupled 1D-3D simulations at default visual predation risk configuration (**D1.4**), variations of **D1.4** under different visual predation risk configurations (**D1.5**), scientific publications (**D1.6**), conference presentations (**D1.7**).

WP2: Improving the model by bridging the resolution gap between mechanistic and empirical data

Members: Basedow (lead, UiT), Priou (APN), Thorstensen (APN), Bandara (APN), Ohman (mentor, UCSD)

RQ2: How do **WP1**'s model predictions improve when validated with empirical data of comparable spatio-temporal and biological resolution?

H2: Empirical data with comparable spatial, temporal and biological resolution can significantly improve the present-day mechanistic predictions of diel vertical migration (**H2.1**), seasonal vertical migration (**H2.2**) and vertical carbon export (**H2.3**) of the study area.

Approach: While **WP1**'s SIBM may produce reasonable present-day estimates of *C. finmarchicus* DVM & SVM and resultant vertical carbon export (**H1 = true**), there is a good chance that such predictions may go wrong (**H1 = false**). The SIBM thus needs to be validated with empirical data to improve their reliability, accuracy and precision (collectively, the predictive potential). However, the coupled 3D bio-physical simulations of **WP1**

produces data with high spatio-temporal and biological resolution while covering an annual timespan across a large geographical region (Fig. 1). Model data with such spatio-temporal resolution and coverage are not comparable to classic plankton-net samples collected onboard research vessels⁶⁴. However, optical and acoustic zooplankton observation techniques produces data with comparable spatio-temporal resolution to simulation models⁶⁵. Since the biological resolution of zooplankton net samples are far superior to any state-of-the-art optical or acoustic zooplankton observation system, a combination of these sampling and in-situ observation techniques can offer a promising alternative for model validation by bridging the resolution gap between mechanistic and empirical data. To increase the spatio-temporal coverage of empirical data, we will: (i) perform classic zooplankton sampling (shipboard survey) across the study area, (ii) mount the optical and acoustic sensors onto autonomous surface and underwater vehicles (autonomous survey) moving in the study area intermittently over an annual cycle and (iii) reuse zooplankton data from Continuous Plankton Recorder survey (CPR) and from previous projects (GLIDER phase-I).

Methodology: We will collect: (i) *C. finmarchicus* individuals in depth-stratified vertical net hauls using a MultiNet (Type Midi: Hydrobios, Kiel) and (ii) larger zooplankton and fish larvae using WP-3 net and/or a Tucker Trawl plankton net from coastal and offshore stations across the study area on board the research vessel ‘Beret Paulsdatter’ of UiT – The Arctic University of Norway (Fig. 3). The water column will also be profiled for subsurface irradiance, temperature and Chlorophyll-*a* (proxy of phytoplankton concentration) using a CTD with an affixed fluorometer (SeaBird Electronics Inc.). We will scrutinize the vertical distribution and acoustic densities of fish using the research vessel’s hull-mounted echosounder (Simrad EK80: 38–120 kHz). Altogether, three (3 × 3 days) shipboard sampling excursions will be performed, two during the productive season (focusing on active *C. finmarchicus* in the upper pelagial) and one during the unproductive season (focusing on diapausing *C. finmarchicus* in deeper layers). For the autonomous survey, two autonomous vehicles, the Sailbuoy (Offshore Sensing AS) and Seaglider M1 (Kongsberg Maritime AS) will be used (Fig. 4). The Sailbuoy is an autonomous surface vehicle equipped with a high-frequency broadband echosounder (Simrad EK80 WBT-mini: 142–285 kHz), a CT-sensor to measure near-surface temperature and salinity (Neil Brown Ocean Sensors Inc.) and an Odessey Xtream irradiance (400–700 nm) intensity logger (Dataflow Systems Ltd.). Based on our previous experience, the high frequency range of the echosounder is optimal for detecting larger copepods, such as *C. finmarchicus* maximally down to ca. 100 m depth^{17,66}. To estimate the abundance and vertical distribution of *C. finmarchicus*, we will resolve the identities of the sound scatterers with an Underwater Vision Profiler v.6 (UVP 6⁶⁷) mounted on the Seaglider (which captures images of zooplankton along its path) and with nets deployed from the ship. Since the Seaglider is an autonomous underwater vehicle that does undulating (yo-yo) dives, we will synchronize the paths of the two autonomous vehicles in a way that the: (i) diving Seaglider trails the surface operating Sailbuoy and (ii) Seaglider complements the ‘blind-zone’ of the Sailbuoy and provides optical coverage across the water column (Fig. 4). This synchrony will provide a near-continuous optical data stream to groundtruth the acoustic data that aids in resolving the identities of vertical migrants. Altogether, UVP 6 vertical profiles and EK80 acoustic data will allow us to estimate the timing and amplitude of *C. finmarchicus* DVMs across the study area^{17,68}. In line with the shipboard survey, we will use the synchronized autonomous-vehicle-duo in two deployments (2 × 25 days) covering the productive season, when *C. finmarchicus* populations are predominant in the upper pelagial. During the unproductive season, when much of the *C. finmarchicus* population is at diapause depths, we will deploy the Seaglider to perform several dives in the range of 600–1000 m in the deep Norwegian Sea basin to detect diapausing *C. finmarchicus* populations & mesopelagic visual predators (Fig. 3). Here, for better abundance and diapause depth estimations, we will downward-mount a high-frequency echosounder (Kongsberg EK80 WBT-mini: 142–285 kHz) on the Seaglider alongside the UVP 6 (Fig. 3). The UVP 6 offers the potential to evaluate diapause of *C. finmarchicus* in-situ, from their posture and orientation in the water column⁶⁹. To further span spatio-temporal gaps in empirical data, we will reuse near-

Fig. 3 Proposed shipboard survey of WP2, which uses various plankton nets to collect *C. finmarchicus* down to diapause depths. A Seaglider with optical and acoustic sensors will also be sent to these depths for in-situ observations.

Fig. 4 The proposed upper-pelagial autonomous survey of WP2, which uses path-synchronized autonomous surface vehicle carrying an acoustic sensor and an underwater vehicle equipped with an optical sensor for *in-situ* observation of *C. finmarchicus*. Figure not to scale.

finmarchicus & fish estimated from net hauls and hull-mounted echosounder. **(ii) SVM:** Here, we will mainly use shipboard survey data, which provides accurate characterizations of *C. finmarchicus* body size, developmental stage and energy reserve size (total lipid content) over the study area from both productive and unproductive seasons. A comparative assessment of these will allow us to draw inferences about the periodicity and amplitude of SVM and diapause duration^{24,71}. As the vertical spatial resolution of plankton net data is coarse, we will use the *in-situ* optical and acoustic observations made by the deep-diving Seaglider to get better estimates of *C. finmarchicus* seasonal migration amplitudes **(iii). Vertical carbon export:** Estimates of vertical carbon export below the photic zone by vertically migrating *C. finmarchicus* will be adopted from two different ecosystem models operating in the region (see below).

To test **H2**, we will compare the model-predicted dynamics of DVM – **H2.1** and SVM – **H2.2** with corresponding empirical estimates. We will compare the vertical carbon export estimates of our unconstrained model with those from NORWECOM (with constrained vertical migrations) and SINMOD (with no vertical migrations) – **H2.3**. If the model predictions deviate considerably from empirical estimates (**H2 = true**), we will use environmental correlates of the observed behavioural and life history patterns to tune the SIBM. Model tuning mainly include (i). updating time- and space-specific the biological attributes (e.g., developmental stage composition, numerical abundance, body size, total lipid content, fecundity), (ii). imposing and relaxation of constraints, changing functions and parameters, (iii). adjustment of environmental variables and (iv). adding alternative patterns of vertical behaviour (e.g., schooling, reverse diel vertical migration).

Risk management: The autonomous survey of **WP2** carries a risk of platform and data loss while at sea. The probability of such an unfortunate event occurring is quite low, as both Sailbuoy and Seaglider have been rigorously field-tested and widely used for long-term, all-weather data collection in many previous projects without issues. However, our *C. finmarchicus* vertical migratory characterizations are not solely rendered on autonomous *in-situ* observations, but from multiple data sources, such as the CPR survey and from autonomous observations from previous projects (GLIDER phase-I).

Deliverables: Observed DVM (**D2.1**), SVM (**D2.2**) and life-history (**D2.3**) patterns of the study area, Acoustic data groundtruthing methodology (**D2.4**), validated 1D SIBM (**D2.5**), scientific publications (**D2.6**), conference presentations (**D2.7**).

WP3: Using the improved model to predict future vertical migrations

Members: Bedington (co-lead, APN), Wallhead (co-lead, NIVA), Moyano (NIVA), Pompeii (MIT), Bandara (APN), Halsband (mentor, APN)

RQ3: Will the expected climate-change-related cumulative environmental shifts put *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations and their ecological benefits at crucial crossroads?

H2: The periodicity and amplitude of *C. finmarchicus* DVM (**H3.1**) and SVM (**H3.2**) will significantly change under the cumulative impact of climate-change-related shifts of irradiance, temperature, food and predation environments expected in the study area, thus leading to subsequent changes in vertical carbon export (**H3.3**).

Approach: Most climate change studies of *C. finmarchicus* abundance, behaviour, life-history and biogeography focus on individual environmental variables – mostly temperature, irradiance and food availability (bottom-up selection pressure). Visual predation risk (top-down selection pressure) – a key driver of vertical migrations is

surface *C. finmarchicus* data collected in the CPR survey⁷⁰ and Sailbuoy acoustic data from Norwegian Research Council funded GLIDER project (phase-I).

To achieve **SO2**, we will focus on three different aspects: **(i) DVM:** Here, we will correlate the optical, acoustic & CPR observations of *Calanus finmarchicus* vertical behaviour to environmental data sourced from temperature & Chlorophyll-*a* profiling sensors mounted on the Seaglider, underwater irradiance fields recreated from the surface irradiance estimated on the Sailbuoy and acoustic detections of micronekton (e.g., larval northeast Arctic cod) made on the Sailbuoy. To improve these correlations, we will pull supplementary data from the shipboard survey, which include environmental data profiled by the CTD, abundance and vertical distribution of *C.*

thus often overlooked. Therefore, thorough investigations focusing on the cumulative impacts of climate-change-related irradiance, temperature, food and predation shifts on vertical migrations are significantly lacking. In **WP3**, we will span this knowledge gap by extending the hybrid mechanistic-empirical understanding developed in **WPs 1 & 2** to predict the future dynamics of *C. finmarchicus* DVM & SVM and their ecological consequences (i.e., vertical carbon export) in the study area.

Methodology: We will advect the validated and improved 1D SIBM from **WPs 1 & 2** using forcings from ROMS-ERSEM (A20) 3D physical-biogeochemical model runs for periods in the near, mid-term and distant future under the business-as-usual climate change scenario SSP5-8.5. This climate change scenario is chosen because current emissions are tracking close to its pathway⁷². For recent (2026–2035) and mid-term (2046–2055) periods, we will reuse dynamical downscaling projections developed during the EU-funded project TAPAS⁶⁰ which are currently being refined within JPI Oceans project CE2COAST. For distant future period, we will run these downscaling projections for years between 2085–2100 in **WP3**. As in **WP1**, we will extract time- and space-specific seawater velocity components, irradiance, temperature and phytoplankton concentrations over the annual cycle for our study area from each of these ROMS-ERSEM (A20) future scenario simulations. The 1D SIBM will be advected across the study area for each of these selected future seascapes representing near, mid-term & distant future. To achieve **SO3**, we will run multiple model simulations (simulation experiments) to test how temperature-, irradiance- and food-driven bottom-up selection pressure shifts will interact with visual predation risk in the top-down to produce various vertical migratory responses in a future climate. Here, we will configure the visual predation risk following two contrasting assumptions: (i) assuming a static prey size-selectivity where larger prey is always preferred and (ii) dynamic prey-size selectivity where size preference switches based on the body size dynamics of prey (*C. finmarchicus*). For each of these configurations, we will perform model simulations for future years following: (i) present-day visual predation risk intensity and spatio-temporal dynamics (as in **WPs 1 & 2**) and (ii) expected increased visual predation risk intensity and altered spatio-temporal dynamics based on literature⁴⁶ and publicly available acoustic and fish trawl datasets from ICES-coordinated surveys. Through these simulation experiments, we will check how *C. finmarchicus* DVM (**H3.1**) & SVM (**H3.2**) and the resultant vertical carbon export below the photic zone (**H3.3**) would shift in response to cumulative bottom-up and top-down environmental forcing in the study area by the end of this century.

Deliverables: Modelled future environmental dynamics (**D3.1**), Emergent DVM (**D3.2**), SVM (**D3.3**) and vertical carbon export (**D3.4**) in future environments, variations of DVM, SVM & vertical carbon export under different visual predation risks (**D3.5**), scientific publications (**D3.6**), conference presentations (**D3.7**).

WP4: Data management and communications

Members: Borch (lead, APN), Helgeland (APN), Seo (–), Brabaharan (UOR), Bandara (APN), with inputs from all project members.

Approach: To achieve **SO4**, we will follow a three-tier approach that ensures: (i) proper storage and management of data during project activities, (i) open access to data, models and methods generated/used in the project and (ii). effective communication of project activities and outputs to target audiences.

Methodology: *Data management:* Migratory Crossroads will produce significant amounts of mechanistic and empirical data. To store these data during project activities (e.g., model simulations, model analyses, validation, empirical data processing), we will use cloud storage services of the NIRD (National e-Infrastructure for Research Data) *via* the service platform operated by Sigma2. This minimizes the need to move data between physical drives and the cloud because NIRD Toolkit allows running web-based tools for data processing and analyses, such as Jupyter and RStudio (= our preferred analytical platforms). *Open access to data, models & methods (see also Section 2.1):* All of our mechanistic and empirical data (raw & processed) will be archived under the CC By 4.0 public licence in Sigma2's long-term RDA (Research Data Archive). RDA allows users to browse and download data anonymously using the Sigma2's 'searching web interface'. Model source codes (FORTRAN) will be made openly available in a dedicated GitHub repository. Data processing pipelines, analytical codes (Jupyter notebooks for Python and RStudio markdown files), visualizations, project summaries and highlights will be archived in a dedicated Zenodo repository, to which the above GitHub repository will be linked. *Communications (see also Section 2.3):* In Migratory Crossroads, we distinguish three target audiences: (i) scientific community, (ii) industry & management stakeholders and (iii) general public. Project findings will be communicated to the scientific community through Open Access scientific publications, and oral & poster presentations at international scientific conferences and meetings. As our findings have implications for commercial fisheries and the management of *C. finmarchicus* as well as other commercial fish stocks, we will be in dialogue with industry partners, such as Zooca[®] (*Calanus* harvesting company) as well as management authorities such as the Directorate of Fisheries and the Norwegian Coastal Administration who administers the BarentsWatch Information System. This dialogue will be ensured through a digital workshop at project mid-term and an in-person meeting the end

of the project, which will be a side-event at the Arctic Frontiers conference. To communicate interesting project developments and findings to the general public, we will differentially-target two age groups: (i) children & teenagers and (ii) adults. To generate interest and increase awareness of children & teenagers in marine sciences, climate change, zooplankton and fish, we will organize pictures & videos of fieldwork, animations and infographics (e.g., simplified data visualizations & conceptual diagrams) into a visual exhibit that will be launched in annual National Research Days in Norway and similar events at the Science Attraction Centre-Polaria in Tromsø. Further, we will collaborate with a software engineer with a marine science background (see Section 3.1) to develop a digital game targeted at younger audiences called 'Catch the Calanus', where players get to play the role of different predators and level-up along the trophic hierarchy (e.g., from carnivorous copepods, jellyfish, fish, seabirds and up to baleen whales – each with unique ‘catching’ abilities) while trying to catch as many *C. finmarchicus* individuals as possible. In the game, the role of *Calanus* will be played by the system (processor), which will impose different behavioural and life history tactics as counter measures. To extend our outreach to adult audiences, we will work closely with a communications expert and a freelance science journalist (see Section 3.1) to publish interesting findings of the project in national (e.g., forskning.no, ScienceNordic, Sciencenorway.no, and the Tromsø Fram Centre journal Fram Forum) and international (e.g., Knowable Magazine, Scientific American, Wired) popular science outlets. As a common means of pushing project updates, activities and findings to all the above target audiences, we will use social media channels, such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Discord & YouTube and a project webpage.

Deliverables: Cloud storage of research data during processing (D4.1), Open Access research data, model source codes, & methods (D4.2), workshops/webinars (D4.3), ‘Catch the Calanus’ digital game (D4.4), infographics & video (D4.5), popular science news & articles (D4.6), social media and project webpage updates (D4.7).

1.3 Novelty and ambition

Although DVM & SVM of *C. finmarchicus* is a major part of the greatest synchronized animal migration of our planet, these migrations have been either entirely disregarded or overly simplified in disregarded in ecosystem models, management decisions and in climate change impact assessments. This unfortunate omission and oversimplification of vertical migrations in ecosystem models is mainly due to the higher computational demands of simulating greater biological complexity. In Migratory Crossroads, we will go beyond the current state-of-the-art by employing the highest biologically detailed model available for *C. finmarchicus* behavioural and life-history simulations in our coupled 1D–3D model simulations. This has been made possible by continuous developments and performance upgrades made to the 1D IBM since 2018 by its main architect, Bandara who is the project lead (and WP1 lead) of Migratory Crossroads^{13,34,56}. Here, the elevated computational demands of simulating unconstrained behavioural and life-history detail are managed using streamlined computer code alongside novel high-performance computing techniques that harness the power of cutting-edge computational hardware. Our modelling system not only predicts *C. finmarchicus* DVM & SVM responses under the cumulative impact of environmental variability but enables us to adjust or turn-off the influence of visual predation risk – so, the top-down selection pressures can be de-coupled from the bottom-up. We also employ a novel and unique way of model validation, which attempts to bridge the resolution gap between mechanistic and empirical data – a major challenge in ecological modelling⁷³. Here, rather than solely relying on classic shipboard data collection methods, we aim to implement a state-of-the-art autonomous vehicle survey to monitor *C. finmarchicus* vertical migrations in an interference-free environment (because autonomous vehicles used in our study ensure silent and dark operation). We will go beyond the current state-of-the-art and synchronize the paths of autonomous surface vehicle and the underwater vehicle, which will facilitate a near-continuous groundtruthing of the acoustic data. This will be the first time that such multi-vehicle synchrony is used in a large-scale ecological data collection. To span the mechanistic-empirical resolution gap further, we will reuse relevant data from openly available domains, such CPR survey, ICES-coordinated fish-trawl & acoustics surveys and previous projects. Being a project oriented on climate change, we attempt to minimize the carbon emissions of our project by reducing the shipboard sampling (3 × 3 days) in favour of emission-free autonomous vehicle survey (2 × 25 days). Further, our attempt to reuse data wherever possible (e.g., ROMS-ERSEM 3D model simulations, abundance & vertical distribution data of *C. finmarchicus* and fish) significantly cuts down on: (i) redundant field surveys and carbon emissions therein and (ii) energy demands of performing thousands of redundant computational cycles. At a time when greenhouse gas emissions and energy prices are on the rise, we believe that a data reuse initiative is well justified.

2. Impact

2.1 Potential academic impact of the research project

Although over a century has passed since DVM & SVM of *C. finmarchicus* were first documented², it is still unclear how these migrations will respond to climate-change-related environmental shifts. By bridging this knowledge gap, Migratory Crossroads will advance our understanding of how co-varying environmental drivers

would impact *C. finmarchicus* ecology and evolution in future high-latitude oceans. As our SIBM allows an unconstrained behavioural and life-history representation, it will provide the most accurate estimate of vertical carbon export by *C. finmarchicus* to-date, which is essential for predicting the biological pump's future climate change buffering capacity⁷. Our findings will thus attract a broad scientific audience in the fields of zooplankton ecology, climatology, biological & physical oceanography, behavioural & evolutionary ecology, fisheries biology and biogeochemical cycling. Since the multidisciplinary methodological drive of Migratory Crossroads leverages the potential of cutting-edge mechanistic and empirical research, it will have implications in the fields of ecological modelling, autonomous ocean observation, marine optics and bioacoustics, and will be re-employed many times in the future. A major force driving the academic impact of Migratory Crossroads is the competency of the project group. Here, we blend the skills of several emerging early- and mid-career scientists with the vast experience in plankton ecology and evolution of Ohman, Halsband, Varpe and Basedow (see Section 3.1), who have contributed significantly to the zooplankton vertical migratory knowledgebase over the last few decades. Altogether, our approach, methods and competence will produce a strong and impactful synthesis on the climate change impacts of the greatest synchronized animal movement of our planet. For an enduring academic impact, we will adhere to the Norwegian Research Council's Open Science policy by making our data, models, methods, and research publications openly available (see WP4). In this regard, our chosen Open Access archive (Sigma2 RDA) will ensure long-term persistence of the data, which allows our research outputs to be reused and cross-checked for validity and reproducibility. We will improve the findability of the archived research data by producing metadata according to the Dublin Core standard (which is a feature of RDA). Further, Sigma2's data management architectures contains a rigorous interoperability framework that allows our data to be accessed and processed from multiple sources & systems without losing its integrity. This FAIR data principle is also reflected in Zenodo repositories, where we will deposit our models and methods (see WP4). Apart from these practices, in Migratory Crossroads, we will strictly adhere to the principle that our findings will only be published in Open Access scientific journals (see Section 2.3 for further details). To ensure that these Open Science practices are rigorously maintained in the project, we have designed a specific work package (WP4) and appointed personnel with data management and communications expertise (see Sections 3.1 & 3.2). Our Open Science practices will ensure that Migratory Crossroads is not an ultimate solution but a baseline that allows further modifications. The current spatial extent can be expandable to a pan-Arctic scale, and it will be possible to couple this lower-trophic level modelling system to a larger ecosystem model. Consequently, the academic impact of Migratory Crossroads will not be limited to the scope of this proposal but will reverberate within the academic community for many years to come.

2.2 Potential for societal impact of the research project

At its core, the aims of Migratory Crossroads align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UNSDG) no. 13: climate action because we: (i) attempt to understand the responses of a keystone copepod species to climate-change-driven environmental variability and (ii) assess the implication of above responses in buffering future climatic changes *via* the biological carbon pump. This understanding is crucial when adopting climate policies (Target 13.2: *Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning*). It also has implications in UNSDG no. 12: responsible consumption & productions (Target 12.2: *Achieving sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources*). This is because: (i) *C. finmarchicus* is harvested in the study area as a source of food and (ii) it is a main source of food for many commercially harvested fish species in the study area (Fig. 1). If future environmental shifts would drive considerable changes in behavioural and life-history strategies among herbivorous zooplankton, they will in-turn drive abundance, biomass and phenology (i.e., timing of life cycle events) shifts among higher-order consumers through trophic interactions. Migratory Crossroads aims to foresee such changes among *C. finmarchicus* – a key trophic link between primary producers and many commercially harvested fish species of the Norwegian and Barents Seas, so that future ecological shifts do not come as a surprise and management measures are early-adopted in response. Findings of Migratory Crossroads will therefore: (i) contribute to sustainable harvesting of *C. finmarchicus* in the long-run and (ii) support the ongoing forecasting and management of fisheries resources in the Norwegian and Barents Seas. Therefore, management implications of Migratory Crossroads will be crucial in developing an ocean policy aimed at adopting a sustainable blue economy. Migratory Crossroads will also help to span a key knowledge gap of the Norwegian and Barents Sea management plans, which state “*It is important to learn more about the pace and impacts of climate change and ocean acidification and about the factors that influence the resilience of the ecosystem to change*”. Altogether, the objectives, planned activities and deliverables of the proposed project (see Section 3.2) directly align with the UNSDG no. 14: life below water – where ocean-borne resource management, climate change mitigation and increasing scientific knowledge and developing & implementation marine monitoring technologies are some of the frontal priorities (Targets 14.2, 14.4 and 14a). Migratory Crossroads will also fit the vision and mission of 2021–2030 UN Ocean Decade – a framework for creating knowledge and solutions for ocean's pressing problems. While the proposed outcomes of WPs 1–3 will support Ocean Decade

challenge no. 2 (Protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity), no. 3 (Sustainably feed the global population), no. 4 (Develop a sustainable and equitable ocean economy) and no. 5 (Unlock ocean-based solutions to climate change), the broad outreach in WP4 will support challenge no. 9 (Skills, knowledge, and technology for all) and no. 10 (Change humanity's relationship with the ocean).

2.3 Measures for communication and exploitation

Communication of our findings to target audiences is a key objective in Migratory Crossroads (SO4). Therefore, as described in WP4, we will distinguish different target audiences and use tailored communications channels to reach out to them (see WP4 in Section 1.2 for details). For scientific communication, we will adhere to the Norwegian Research Council's Open Science policy by publishing the findings of our project solely in Open Access scientific journals or those with transformative Open Access agreements (publishable under CC BY 4.0 license). Apart from the publishable science, we will: (i) allow open access to our data, models and methods, thus adhering to the FAIR data principles (see WP4 & Section 2.1 for details) and (ii) broaden our scientific outreach by attending relevant conferences and meetings. Further, we will rely on workshops/webinars to communicate our findings to industrial and management level stakeholders (see WP4). Since Migratory Crossroads focuses on a great migration of an important animal for the marine ecosystem, we think that the project will be of interest to the general public. For popular outreach we will build on visual and immersive approaches, such as infographics, videos and a digital game (see WP4). With both text and visuals, we will leverage the potential of social media as a tool that can reach out to all target audiences.

3. Implementation

3.1 Project manager and project group

Migratory Crossroads will be led by Dr. Kanchana Bandara (lead WP1), an early-career researcher, specializes in behavioural and life history modelling of high-latitude zooplankton. He has considerable experience in working with shipboard sampling, marine bioacoustics & high-performance computing. Bandara has seven peer-reviewed first-author publications, six of which are in Tier-1 scientific journals, including a comprehensive review of zooplankton vertical migrations in Biological Reviews². The project group and their core competencies are listed in Table 1. They represent four Norwegian and three overseas universities and research institutions.

Table 1: The project group, their institutional (IN), gender (GN) and work-package (WP) affiliations and roles in the project

Member	IN	GN	WP	Competence	Role in the project
Dr. Kanchana Bandara ^{*(CV)}		M	■ ■ ■	Early-career plankton ecologist & modeller: see description above	Project PI, lead WP1 SIBM design, data processing, sampling
Dr. Claudia Halsband ^(CV)		F	■	Biological oceanographer with extensive experience in <i>Calanus</i> ecology	Mentor WP3
Dr. Michael Bedington*	APN	M	■ ■	Early-career numerical modeler specializing in coastal hydrodynamics and Lagrangian particle tracking	Co-lead WP3 1D-3D model coupling
Pierre Priou*		M	■	Early-career researcher specializing in marine bioacoustics	Bioacoustics
Trude Borch ^(CV)		F	■	Social scientist with significant experience with management-oriented research, stakeholder dialogue and popular-science communications	Lead WP4 Communications
Conrad Helgeland		M	■	An experienced data engineer	Data management
Morten Thorstensen		M	■	Specialist in marine technology and autonomous vehicle operations	Autonomous platforms
Dr. Philip Wallhead ^(CV)	NIVA	M	■ ■	Oceanographer specializing in marine bio-geochemical modelling	Co-lead WP3 ROMS model & data
Dr. Marta Moyano ^(CV)		F	■ ■	Marine ecologist specializing in bottom-up impacts on fish and plankton populations	Visual predation risk configurations
Assoc. Prof. Sünneje Basedow	UIT	F	■	Marine ecologist with extensive experience in <i>Calanus</i> ecology, remote sensing, plankton sampling and optics	Lead WP2 Plankton nets & optics
Prof. Øystein Varpe ^(CV)	NINA	M	■	An evolutionary ecologist with extensive experience in behavioural & life-history modelling	Mentor WP1
Prof. Mark Ohman ^(CV)	UCSD	M	■	A world-renowned biological oceanographer with paramount experience in plankton ecology	Mentor WP2
Dr. Camila Serra Pompeii ^{*(CV)}	MIT	F	■ ■	Early-career marine ecologist specializing in marine plankton and vertical carbon export	SIBM design, vertical carbon export
Hannah Seo	–	F	■	Freelance science journalist, essayist, podcast writer, poet and a reporting fellow for the New York Times	Popular-science communications
Varshani Brabharan ^{*(CV)}	UOR	F	■	Research assistant (oceanography) and a software engineer	'Catch the <i>Calanus</i> ' game design

APN: Akvaplan niva, NIVA: Norsk institutt for vannforskning, NINA: Norsk institutt for naturforskning, UIT: Arctic University of Norway, UCSD: Scripps Institute of Oceanography, University of California San Diego, MIT: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, UOR: University of Ruhuna. * Early-career researcher. ^(CV) CV attached in the online application. ■ WP1 ■ WP2 ■ WP3 ■ WP4.

The project group is near-gender-balanced and consists of 7 (47%) females and 8 (53%) males. Further, 2/4 (50%) work-package leaders are females and 5/15 (33.3%) of the project group members are early-career scientists (Table 1).

3.2 Project organization and management

Roles of project members in each work package is listed in Table 1. Bandara will be involved in all four work packages with a total employment equivalent to 25% of the project

duration. Contributions of senior researchers of the group (Ohman, Halsband, Varpe and Basedow) will be used throughout the project. UIT guarantees ship-time for the field excursions. Autonomous vehicles and sensor payloads will be rented from and operated by APN. Model simulations will be run in high-performance computing facilities of Sigma2. Data storage and archiving in Sigma2 NIRD and RDA, respectively (see WP4). All software (applications) used for data processing will be open source. The project will run for **36 months** from **1 January 2024** to **31 December 2026** (Fig. 5). Migratory Crossroads will begin with a kick-off meeting and with the launch of its own webpage (Fig. 5). While work-package leaders will meet (online) once a month to review the project progress and address challenges, the entire project group will meet once a year.

Fig. 5 Timeline of main activities planned under different work packages of Migratory Crossroads. **D:** Deliverable (see work package descriptions in Section 1.2 for details).

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